

Enhancing access and understanding of ancient manuscripts: the 3D Digital Edition of the Codex Cospi

Alice Bordignon^{a*}, Davide Domenici^b

^a*Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Via Zamboni, 32, 40126, Bologna, BO, Italy*

^b*Department of History and Cultures, University of Bologna, Piazza San Giovanni in Monte, 2, 40124, Bologna, BO, Italy*

*Corresponding author: Alice Bordignon, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Via Zamboni, 32, 40126, Bologna, BO, Italy, alice.bordignon2@unibo.it

Declarations of interest: none

ABSTRACT

Engaging museum visitors with ancient manuscripts poses challenges due to preservation requirements, inaccessible language, and fragility, which prevents physical interaction. This study explores innovative solutions through two research questions: RQ1, how can 3D enhance traditional 2D representations of ancient manuscripts? RQ2, how can a reliable and engaging 3D knowledge space be created to facilitate their understanding? The 3D Digital Edition (3DDE) of the Codex Cospi, a Mesoamerican divinatory manuscript with a complex leporello structure, illustrates the value of 3D digitisation in capturing and presenting intricate layouts. By integrating interdisciplinary research and employing storytelling techniques, the 3DDE creates an interactive virtual resource accessible to diverse audiences. Bridging accessibility and scholarly reliability, the 3DDE proves suitable for museum exhibitions, education, and research, providing an engaging and enriched understanding of the Codex's historical and cultural significance.

KEYWORDS:

3d digital edition; 3d modelling; codex cospi; manuscripts; digital cultural heritage object

1. Introduction

Conveying the significance of manuscripts to museum visitors presents several challenges. Preservation requirements often necessitate dim lighting, the language of the texts can be inaccessible, and the fragile nature of manuscripts prevents physical handling. As a result, visitors tend to engage with these works primarily for their aesthetic value, particularly when adorned with intricate decorations. While some museums offer 2D digital galleries to showcase manuscript pages, these tools frequently lack engaging storytelling elements or interactive features, which hinders deeper visitor engagement and understanding (Schreibman and Papadopoulos, 2019; Pietroni et al., 2023).

Over the last three decades, the cultural heritage sector has increasingly adopted interactive 3D models as tools for knowledge production. These technologies allow scholars to make complex two-dimensional data more comprehensible and to simulate conditions (spatial, temporal, or material) that cannot be addressed through conventional methods (Schreibman and Papadopoulos, 2019). The ability to digitally manipulate a representation of an object faithful to its physical characteristics introduces new opportunities for access, discovery and valorisation of fragile and inaccessible artefacts, particularly when combined with effective storytelling techniques and contextual information (Bekele et al., 2018; Rizvic et al., 2024). A successful digital representation should go beyond mere photorealism to provide insights into an artefact's creation, historical relevance, and social or cultural significance. In this context, while photorealism aligns with public expectations and is often associated with historical accuracy, user evaluations suggest that intuitive and consistent interaction in a digital environment is more effective for learning than a focus on photorealistic detail (Pujol-Tost, 2019).

According to Huurderman and Piccoli (2021), the use of 3D models as research tools enables a potential iterative three-step process of knowledge creation, sharing, and discovery:

1. New insights emerge during the creation of a 3D reconstruction (interpretative visualisation).
2. This knowledge is presented to viewers through an online or immersive platform (expressive visualisation).
3. Users interact with the 3D environment, gaining, discovering, and even contributing new knowledge by exploring underlying linked data.

Based on these premises, this work seeks to address two key research questions:

- RQ1: How can 3D enhance traditional 2D representations of ancient manuscripts?
- RQ2: How can a reliable and engaging 3D knowledge space be created to facilitate their understanding?

This paper focuses on the interdisciplinary study and on the creation of the 3D Digital Edition (3DDE) of the Codex Cospi, a Mesoamerican divinatory manuscript. The aim is to integrate existing research from various fields into a single, accessible, and interactive virtual space, leveraging storytelling techniques to engage multiple audiences across reliable sources. The 3DDE of the Codex Cospi aspires to serve as a tool for knowledge production, cultural valorisation, and public and academic dissemination.

The article will be structured as follows: section 2 gives a brief overview of the current state of the art in using innovative technologies to study and valorise ancient manuscripts from an international point of view. Section 3 will introduce the methodology employed for the manuscript's digitisation within the CHANGES project (Spoke 4) and the development of the 3DDE using the methodological framework and infrastructure created by the PURE3D project. Section 4 presents the planned future improvements of the prototype presented. Finally, in Section 5, we discuss the main results obtained in our research.

2. Related works

The need to explore new approaches for accessing, enriching, and presenting ancient manuscripts (and generally texts) emerged after the development of the World Wide Web (Schreibman and Schoueri, 2024). Digital Scholarly Editions (DSEs) were among the earliest scholarly artefacts created by humanists to address this need, which stems from a long tradition of editing texts for print publication (Apollon et al., 2014; Driscoll and Pierazzo, 2016). DSE can be defined as assemblages or machines of knowledge which have introduced new modalities for annotation, extending beyond text to encompass audio, video, and images, linking data across internal and external, cross-media sources. Most of these editions

were primarily text-based, employing the conventions of the Text Encoding Initiative (<https://tei-c.org/>) (e.g., The Rossetti Archive (<https://www.rossettiarchive.org/>), The Walt Whitman Archive (<https://whitmanarchive.org/>), among others), while a smaller number focused on image-based editions, such as The Blake Archive (<https://www.blakearchive.org/>). DSE redefined the role of text-based editions, shifting them from static, confined environments (such as books) into expansive, interconnected digital spaces.

This transformation allows for the creation of digital archives that assemble texts around specific themes, individuals, or topics, extending their context into a multimodal and dynamic space for exploration (Schreibman and Papadopoulos, 2019). However, these editions often maintain a predominantly critical focus, without developing storytelling methodologies to make their content more engaging for a wider audience. Furthermore, they frequently fail to fully leverage the potential for interdisciplinary collaboration, concentrating primarily on critical, philological, literary, and historical aspects. In this context, projects like MINIARE, at the Fitzwilliam Museum, Cambridge, (<https://fitzmuseum.cam.ac.uk/research/projects/miniare>) focus on supporting the collaboration between humanities and hard sciences by enhancing understanding of book artifacts through non-invasive diagnostic techniques. Its web platform enables users to explore manuscripts by accessing insights into the techniques and materials used by illuminators, alongside codicological, palaeographic, and historical-artistic descriptions of the volumes. However, the project presents its content in a static, archival format, focusing on detailed analyses without interactive features or storytelling tools, limiting engagement for non-specialist audiences.

Over the years, advancements in interactive and digital technologies have offered textual scholars a diverse toolkit for remediating textual records and an expanding array of other knowledge transmission mediums. Among these, virtual technologies prove to be a valuable and engaging asset in providing 3D representations of complex artefacts, adding details and layers of understanding that cannot be achieved through a 2D format (Pallud et al., 2017; Li et al., 2021). Projects like Turning the Page (<https://ttp.onlineculture.co.uk/>) primarily focus on simulating the experience of flipping through a book, digitally reproducing pages in 2D or with basic 3D animations. While this approach provides access to rare manuscripts, it lacks sophisticated narrative tools that could convey the historical, cultural, and artistic contexts surrounding the manuscripts. The emphasis remains on access rather than on creating a deeper, engaging experience.

On the other side, recent projects blend advanced technology to enrich engagement with ancient manuscripts. The MUBIL project, initiated by NTNU University Library and PERCRO in Pisa, (Angelataki et al., 2014) uses 3D technology and gamified environments to promote ancient manuscripts interactively, fostering accessibility and engagement. The USC Virtual Reality Exploration of 15th Century Illuminated Manuscripts (<https://dornsife.usc.edu/xrlab/neh-vr-exploration-of-illuminated-manuscripts/>), developed by the USC Advanced Visualization Lab, immerses users in the artistry and materiality of illuminated texts through VR, fostering interaction and narrative-driven discovery. The Manuscripts of Lichfield (<https://lichfield.ou.edu/content/project>) employs 3D imaging to digitise medieval texts, enhancing public access using 3D galleries and interactive features for scholarly exploration. Finally, Codex4D (<https://codex4d.it/>), developed by the CNR-ISPC, integrates 3D models of manuscripts into virtual and mixed-reality environments, combining hidden textual layers, subsurface details, and material diagnostics to create an interdisciplinary and web-based interaction powered by ATON framework (Fanini et al., 2021; Schettino et al., 2023; Pietroni et al., 2023). Except few cases, 3D models are presented through videos with audio narration, shared on platforms (e.g., YouTube) or displayed in museums. While this approach is accessible and widely disseminated, it limits the 3D models' integration into the broader public and scholarly ecosystem (Schreibman and Papadopoulos, 2019). Moreover, the few accessible 3D models are mostly presented through interfaces with limited functionality, where the assets are only occasionally supplemented with predominantly textual content. Despite the milestones achieved by the mentioned projects, the lack of robust design strategies (such as storytelling techniques) highlights the need to adopting a methodology capable of making content accessible to a broader audience beyond the academic community. At the same time, building on past efforts, it remains essential to ensure reliable content and accurate digital representations through transparent documentation following the FAIR principles (Knazook et al., 2023). Finally, while text-based editions benefit from decades-old standards and established research communities, such as the Text Encoding Initiative, working with more complex sources like 3D models presents distinct challenges (Moore et al., 2022). In this context, the absence of a stable web-based environment and widely accepted community-based standards, particularly concerning schema, metadata, and paradata, creates additional hurdles for the analysis, study, and dissemination of digitised manuscripts (Moore et al., 2022; Schreibman and Schoueri, 2024; Papadopoulos, 2024)

3. Methodology

3.1. *The Codex Cospi*

The Codex Cospi is a pre-Hispanic Mesoamerican pictorial manuscript now in the University Library in Bologna (inv. 4093) (Anders et al., 1994; Laurencich Minelli, 1992). Probably painted in the Eastern Nahuatl regions of Puebla-Tlaxcala (Mexico) between the fifteenth and early sixteenth centuries, it was brought to Bologna in 1533 by the Dominican friar Domingo de Betanzos (Domenici and Laurencich, 2014). The manuscript is a tonalamatl, or “book of destinies”, a ritual object used in divinatory performances related to calendrical and astronomical events. It consists of a 364 cm-long strip of animal skin, likely deer, made up of five pieces and folded into a *leporello* format to form 20 plates. Both sides are covered with plaster and painted, though in different regions and with distinct color palettes primarily based on organic dyes (Miliani et al., 2012). The obverse of the codex, read from left to right, contains a 260-day divinatory calendar, predictions tied to Venus’s heliacal rise, and depictions of the four quarters of the ritual year. The reverse, read from right to left, likely served as divination tables or as instructions for the proper disposal of offerings during rituals associated with several animals, with the content oriented 180° from the obverse. The leporello structure, typical of pre-Hispanic Mesoamerican manuscripts, allows the reader to open a varying number of plates so that a complete section could be displayed during the ritual action. Yet, the codex’s dual-sided nature, and complex layout are difficult to convey in a 2D edition. In this context, we envisioned that a 3D format could enhance understanding by situating information within its spatial context, offering insights into the codex’s complex format, and enabling users to intuitively appreciate its intricate structure and ritual functionality through enriched contextual information.

The Codex’s 3D digital representation was created as part of the digital twin developed for the temporary exhibition *The Other Renaissance’: Ulisse Aldrovandi, the Wonders of the World*, (Balzani et al., 2024) following a FAIR-compliant and solid methodology consolidated during the pilot case (Barzaghi et al., 2024; Barzaghi et al., 2024a). This work was carried out within the CHANGES project (“Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Gen Sustainable Society”), an EU-funded national initiative. More specifically, it was part of SPOKE 4, the thematic sub-project dedicated to employing virtual technologies for the promotion, preservation, exploitation, and enhancement of cultural heritage in museums and art collections.

Due to the preservation state of the Cultural Heritage Object (CHO), it was not possible to use traditional photogrammetric acquisition or scanning techniques to acquire it, as was commonly done in the other cases. Instead, a direct 3D modelling approach was adopted, using specialised software to accurately represent the CHO. For this specific case study, two versions of the model were preserved:

- The Digital Cultural Heritage Object (DCHO): A high-resolution model that represents the most complete version in terms of data density.
- The Optimised Digital Cultural Heritage Object (DCHOo): A more performant 3D model version designed for real-time interaction on web-based platforms.

Every stage of the process required to create the two versions was meticulously documented to ensure full transparency and reproducibility (see Barzaghi et al., 2024; Barzaghi et al., 2024a).

3.2. *3D digitisation process*

The Digital Cultural Heritage Object (DCHO) was generated and modelled in Blender (<https://www.blender.org/>), a free and open-source 3D creation suite, using precise measurements provided by the owning institution and documenting materials about the temporary exhibition where the CHO was exposed. The Codex was depicted fully open to ensure both comprehensive visibility and structural understanding. This approach also faithfully replicates the artefact’s positioning and condition as determined by the curatorial decisions made for the temporary exhibition.

Starting from the RAW version of the photos provided by the University Library of Bologna, some editing operations have been done in GIMP (<https://www.gimp.org/>), an open-source and cross-platform software for image editing, to remove the distortion due to the camera lens to obtain orthogonal images. Then, UV mapping was performed in Blender organising carefully the UV islands to guarantee a detailed texture building using GIMP. UV mapping is the process of linking three-

dimensional mesh coordinates to two-dimensional image coordinates. This involves unwrapping each polygon in the mesh onto a flat surface and applying a texture to it. The texture is an image applied to the surface of a 3D model to accurately reproduce the colours, details, and surface characteristics of the real object.

Fig. 1. Edit view in Blender of the Codex Cospi. On the left, one of the five textures created

To obtain the highest resolution possible, five textures of 16K each were created (Fig. 1), and the UV islands of each of the five UV maps were manually aligned to obtain perfect correspondence between geometry and visual sequencing of textures and, consequently, the plates of the object. This process provides the DCHO, which represents the maximum completeness in terms of data quantity and quality, finally stored in OBJ and FBX format. The DCHO was finally optimised to obtain an additional performant version, the Optimised Digital Cultural Heritage Object (DCHOO), to be used in web-based platforms (i.e., ATON framework, Voyager, etc.) conceived for real-time interaction. The DCHOO is stored in glTF format (<https://www.khronos.org/glTF>), an open and royalty-free specification designed for the efficient transmission of 3D scenes and models between engines and applications (Robinete et al., 2018). The DCHOO was finally published in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) (Bordignon, 2024), an open-access repository for publications and data by researchers. While Zenodo is not specifically designed for 3D or cultural heritage data and metadata, it was selected for its strong alignment with Open Science principles: it offers a DOI for every deposited item, supports advanced metadata schemas such as the DataCite Metadata Schema and Dublin Core, and is highly regarded within the research community.

3.3. 3D Digital Edition

3.3.1 Creating Multifaceted Resources

Each artefact contains a story. In our case, we chose to craft one centred on the Codex Cospi. The PURE3D project (<https://pure3d.eu/>) provided the ideal framework and methodology to achieve this goal, adding a layer of depth to the featured exhibition piece. PURE3D is an open-source infrastructure initiative led by the Maastricht University, The Netherlands. It focuses on revolutionising the presentation, preservation, and evaluation of 3D cultural heritage and scholarly works.

Unlike conventional methods, where 3D models are often presented independently of their academic narratives, PURE3D integrates these models as core scholarly outputs. By embedding them within rich contexts of annotations, multimedia

elements, and metadata, PURE3D turns these models into multifaceted resources that cannot be replicated in traditional print formats. This resource, conceived as a 3D Digital Scholarly Edition, introduces an innovative approach by positioning 3D models as the central "text" within the traditional concept of DSE. This paradigm creates a multimodal space for research and annotation, enhancing accessibility while preserving both the models and their interpretative frameworks as integral components of the scholarly discourse. Creating such an edition involves constructing an intertextual network that integrates the 3D model with its accompanying annotations and apparatus, offering a foundation for the reader to actively participate in the process of knowledge creation (Schreibman and Papadopoulos, 2019). The creation of the 3D Digital Edition required a multidisciplinary approach to integrate different bodies of knowledge. Once the 3D model was created, the authors discussed together the type of textual and visual information to be added, as well as the optimal format and language.

According to Schreibman and Schoueri (2024), 3D digital scholarly editions can be conceptualised as comprising three interoperable layers:

1. The Viewer Layer: The visual interface presented to the user.
2. The Database Layer: Contains the version of the model used in the interface, along with the annotation data and information about object behaviours.
3. The Preservation Layer: Stores all versions of the model created, as well as associated metadata and paradata.

The viewing layer is powered by Smithsonian Voyager (<https://smithsonian.github.io/dpo-voyager/>), a software developed by the Smithsonian Institution to offer immersive online exploration of its 3D digitised collections. The database layer, currently being developed by CLARIAH (<https://www.clariah.nl/>), will enable 3D scholarly editors to create, edit, and publish 3D editions for their audience. Lastly, the preservation layer, guided by DANS (Dutch Data and Archiving Networking Services) (<https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>), ensures long-term accessibility of the 3D edition and its data, even if the viewing or database layers are no longer maintained.

3.3.2 Empathy maps and conceptualisation phase

First, following the methodological framework offered by PURE3D, an empathy map was developed to define the target audience through the creation of personas. Personas are fictional characters that represent groups of similar users, this approach enables to simplify and organise large volumes of user information into more digestible segments (Katifori et al., 2018; Almeshari et al., 2019). In this phase, the main goal is to imagine and learn more about the user and their problems, wants, needs, and the environment or context in which they will experience the design (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Example of User Persona

Then, conceptualisation was needed to identify the main thematic strands on which to structure the edition contents (Fig. 3). Specifically, we identified three main topics based on the available and accessible sources about the Codex Cospi:

1. Contents: covering all aspects related to the interpretation of the manuscript's contents based on research conducted to date.
2. Biography: focusing on the history of the object and its journey from Mesoamerica to the University Library of Bologna, where it is now preserved.
3. Materials: examining the material composition of the object, informed by analyses using innovative technologies conducted thus far (Miliani et al., 2012).

Fig. 3. Conceptualisation phase

Subsequently, we used a PowerPoint presentation to draft the content and keep track of the available materials to enrich each topic. This phase was instrumental in organising the tour's structure and drafting the articles, including their titles, media, captions, and other elements. It also included notes-to-self on how to use hotspot annotations and the 3D space to convey the narrative effectively, such as planned camera movements, viewpoints, and interactions with the 3D model.

3.3.3 Implementation

In 3DDE, annotations can extend beyond text to include multimodal elements and linked data, connecting the edition to knowledge generated externally on the web. Moreover, a dynamic 3D environment offers the unique capability to adjust camera angles and viewpoints, enabling the orchestration of perspectives to highlight and annotate specific physical characteristics of an artefact or its spatial and temporal context. Although the database and preservation layers support the life cycle of a 3DDE, its development and conceptualisation primarily focus on the viewing layer, where both explicit and implicit annotations are integrated with a 3D model of historical or cultural significance (Schreibman and Schoueri, 2024). Huurdeman and Piccoli (2021) suggest that implicit annotations, such as camera views, hypothesis layers, certainty index layers, and texture materials, are created through user interactions with the model and supported by the viewing environment. These annotations differ from explicit ones, such as text, images, sound, or video, as they are less overt or immediately recognisable as editorial contributions.

Voyager, as a 3D web viewer, not only offers tools for inspecting 3D assets (such as zooming, measuring, cross-sectioning, and visual rendering) but also emphasises features that enhance digital storytelling through four interconnected modalities, enabling both linear and nonlinear exploration:

1. Annotation Labels: Expandable hotspot text providing spatially aware annotations.
2. Articles: HTML-based pages incorporating text and multimedia, displayed either as overlays on the 3D model or positioned alongside it.

3. Guided Tours: A versatile mix of annotations, articles, camera movements, and analytical features, including alternative material shaders, lighting adjustments, measurement tools, and slicers.
4. Audio Narration: A single audio clip is available for playback at any point during the experience.

Designed with a general audience in mind, the Codex Cospi 3DDE places a strong emphasis on guided tours. Tours not only offer a step-by-step narrative but also create a rich annotative environment, integrating text, multimedia, and guided camera views to effectively direct the reader's focus. The edition features three thematic tours (Contents, Biography, and Materials) each offering a structured narrative complemented by a richly annotated environment of text and multimedia. These annotations, which include pre-set camera views, are designed to focus the reader's attention on key aspects of the Codex Cospi.

The information, based on the most recent scholarly literature, has been presented in a language accessible to a wide and diverse audience. This need for simplification, without sacrificing scientific accuracy, was particularly effective in dealing with the manuscript's materiality, a task that required making available highly specialised knowledge acquired through spectroscopic analysis. Indeed, in the Materials Tour, the edition integrates a wide array of multimedia resources derived from the analytical campaigns on the manuscript (Miliani et al., 2012). These resources (photos, videos, and scientific papers) are incorporated as explicit annotations, using Voyager's hotspot annotation system, and expanded upon through in-depth articles (Fig. 4). In terms of implicit annotation, the flexible features of Voyager's guided tour enabled us to set specific camera views around the manuscript. These camera movements, combined with object-based contextual annotations (Schreibman and Schoueri, 2024), proved to be the most efficient way to focus attention on the model, highlighting the results of the analysis campaigns conducted on the manuscript. This approach emphasised, based on the color palettes used, the distinct technological traditions of the regions where the two sides of the manuscript were painted (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Article and object-based annotations about Materials

Similarly, within the annotations created for the Content tour, it was possible to directly integrate into the 3D model the interpretations made by scholars regarding the identification of figures and the meaning of the signs or symbols depicted (Fig. 5). Numerous resources (including textual analyses, images, videos, and publications) are interlinked to provide context and narrate the historical and cultural significance of the manuscript. This structure allows users to explore the content through multiple pathways, such as selecting tours, articles, or annotations. Figure 6 illustrates an example of transitioning from an annotation within the Biography Tour to a detailed textual explanation, triggered by clicking the *Read more* function, where additional photos and insights are presented to the user.

To enhance the immersivity and engagement of the tour, as well as improve accessibility for the community of impaired individuals, we are including an MP3 audio file for each article, providing a narrated version of its content. The audio files were generated using Speechgen.io (<https://speechgen.io/it/>), an online AI-powered text-to-speech reader. The platform offers a wide range of synthetic voices and allows users to create and download high-quality audio narrations for free, without licensing issues.

Fig. 5. Article and object-based annotations about Contents

Fig. 6. Example of interactive transition between different sources

3.4 Accessibility and reusability

Voyager supports a variety of formats for 3D model integration and interaction, including glTF and glb for general 3D model rendering, as well as its proprietary SVX format. The SVX format is a structured JSON file designed to manage complex data, including 3D models, annotations, and associated metadata. Its structure is similar to glTF but tailored to the specific needs of Voyager’s ecosystem, enabling rich, multimodal content to be embedded alongside the 3D models. This flexibility allows for the integration of interactive features, like camera views and hotspots, while ensuring that both the models and their interpretative frameworks are preserved and accessible. This makes Voyager’s infrastructure highly replicable for similar projects, as it can support a wide range of digital assets, from text-based annotations to dynamic multimedia resources, all within a streamlined platform for research and engagement.

Using PURE3D interface it is possible to download the entire edition (JSON, Articles, 3D models, multimedia) and replicate it both in the Voyager standalone version (<https://3d.si.edu/voyager-story-standalone>), available online, and through local hosting of Voyager. The standalone version allows users to interact with the content directly via the web, while the local

hosting option provides flexibility for offline access. By hosting Voyager locally, users can run the platform on their own servers, providing full control over the data and ensuring the edition is accessible without an internet connection. This setup enhances the replicability of the project, allowing it to be deployed in various environments, from academic research labs to museum exhibitions, while maintaining the same interactive and multimodal features.

Concerning Codex Cospi digitisation, open software and formats have been used while the process has been carefully documented to enhance transparency and replicability of the methodology in different contexts (Barzaghi et al., 2024; Barzaghi et al., 2024a). While the model has already been published on Zenodo and is available for download, the 3D edition will be made available online through the PURE3D platform, ensuring public accessibility.

4. Future developments

The creation of the 3D edition of the Codex Cospi is an ongoing project. Below, we outline the next planned steps to complete the edition and enhance its potential reception by visitors before its publication:

- Inclusion of audio guides: currently, only the articles related to the contents and partially those on materials include audio guides. Expanding this feature to all content is underway to increase user engagement and improve the immersive experience of the edition.
- Development of a fourth thematic strand: designing a new guided tour focused on the digitisation process used to create the DCHO of the Codex Cospi. This addition aims to strengthen the multidisciplinary aspect of the edition and provide a broader audience with insights into the behind-the-scenes efforts, enhancing transparency in the interpretative processes of reconstruction, metadata curation, and data management.
- Translation into Italian: In addition to the current English version, an Italian version of the edition will be added. Voyager enables the inclusion of scene text in multiple languages, accompanied by corresponding UI language files. With its latest version, Voyager introduced Italian as an available option, specifically requested for this edition. The translation aligns with plans to exhibit the edition during a scheduled 2025 exhibition at the University Library of Bologna, aiming to make the edition accessible to the widest possible audience.
- Planning user assessment methodologies: identifying and implementing appropriate methodologies for evaluating the prototype with real users, such as interviews, surveys, direct observation, and focus groups, to refine and improve the edition.

5. Discussions and Conclusion

The development and promotion of web-based 3D models, enriched with annotations and supporting materials, remain in an early stage of maturity. For ancient manuscripts, the need to provide digital access to these fragile resources must be complemented by offering detailed contextual information to enhance dissemination and understanding for a broader audience.

Addressing RQ1, this case study demonstrates the significant contribution of 3D visualisation for ancient manuscripts, particularly those with complex layouts such as the Codex Cospi. Beyond improving comprehension compared to traditional 2D sources, the 3D representation serves as a valuable tool even in physical exhibitions. During the temporary exhibition *The Other Renaissance*, the placement of the Codex in its display case limited visibility of the reverse side (facing the case). This setup constrained a holistic exploration of the manuscript, which the 3D model resolves by allowing unrestricted and comprehensive interaction with both sides of the object. Additionally, the development of a FAIR-compliant methodology for the manuscript's digitisation aims to make the interpretative process as transparent as possible.

As for RQ2, the 3DDE emerges as an optimal format to go beyond photorealistic representation, creating a cross-media resource that is both comprehensive and engaging. It enhances accessibility while preserving the models and their interpretative frameworks as integral components of scholarly discourse. The inclusion and interconnection of articles, annotations, and multimedia across various thematic strands, supported by storytelling techniques, make the 3D edition of the Codex Cospi a versatile, web-based interdisciplinary resource. Its adaptability aims to ensure relevance across different contexts, from museums and entertainment settings to educational and academic environments. As outlined, the project will be made publicly accessible upon the completion of the planned developments.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the PURE3D team members Costas Papadopoulos, Susan Schreibman, Kelly Gillikin Schoueri, Alicia Walsh, Sohini Mallick; the University Library of Bologna; the Museum of Palazzo Poggi; the Archiginnasio Library of Bologna; the MOLAB mobile laboratory of the Institute for Cultural Heritage (CNR-ISPC). This work has been partially funded by Project PE 0000020 CHANGES - CUP B53C22003780006, NRP Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.3, Funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU.

References

- Almeshari, M., Dowell, J., Nyhan, J., 2019. Using Personas to Model Museum Visitors, in: Adjunct Publication of the 27th Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization. Presented at the UMAP '19: 27th Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization, ACM, Larnaca Cyprus, pp. 401–405. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3314183.3323867>
- Anders, F., Jansen, M., Loo, P. van der, Contreras Martínez, J.E., 1994. Códice Cospi: Biblioteca Universitaria de Bolonia, 4093. Libro explic: Calendario de pronósticos y ofrendas / introd. y explicación: Ferdinand Anders; Maarten Jansen; Peter van der Loo con contrib. de José Eduardo Contreras Martínez, 1. ed. ed, Códices mexicanos. Akad. Dr.- u. Verl.Anst, Graz.
- Angeletaki, A., Carrozzino, M., Johansen, S., 2014. MUBIL: Creating a 3D Experience of “Reading Books” in a Virtual Library Laboratory. *International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era* 3, 271–286. <https://doi.org/10.1260/2047-4970.3.2.271>
- Apollon, D., Belisle, C., Régnier, P. (Eds.), 2014. Digital critical editions, Topics in the digital humanities. University of Illinois Press, Urbana.
- Balzani, R., Barzaghi, S., Bitelli, G., Bonifazi, F., Bordignon, A., Cipriani, L., Colitti, S., Collina, F., Daquino, M., Fabbri, F., Fanini, B., Fantini, F., Ferdani, D., Fiorini, G., Formia, E., Forte, A., Giacomini, F., Girelli, V.A., Gualandi, B., Heibi, I., Iannucci, A., Manganelli Del Fà, R., Massari, A., Moretti, A., Peroni, S., Pescarin, S., Renda, G., Ronchi, D., Sullini, M., Tini, M.A., Tomasi, F., Travaglini, L., Vittuari, L., 2024. Saving temporary exhibitions in virtual environments: The Digital Renaissance of Ulisse Aldrovandi – Acquisition and digitisation of cultural heritage objects. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 32, e00309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.daach.2023.e00309>
- Barzaghi, S., Bordignon, A., Collina, F., Fabbri, F., Fanini, B., Ferdani, D., Gualandi, B., Heibi, I., Mariniello, N., Massari, A., Massidda, M., Moretti, A., Peroni, S., Pescarin, S., Rega, M.F., Renda, G., Sullini, M., 2024. A reproducible workflow for the creation of digital twins in the cultural heritage domain. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14170838>
- Barzaghi, S., Bordignon, A., Gualandi, B., Heibi, I., Massari, A., Moretti, A., Peroni, S., Renda, G., 2024a. A Proposal for a FAIR Management of 3D Data in Cultural Heritage: The Aldrovandi Digital Twin Case. *Data Intelligence*.
- Bekele, M.K., Pierdicca, R., Frontoni, E., Malinverni, E.S., Gain, J., 2018. A Survey of Augmented, Virtual, and Mixed Reality for Cultural Heritage. *J. Comput. Cult. Herit.* 11, 1–36. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3145534>
- Bordignon, A., 2024. Digital twin of the Codex Cospi. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10944120>
- Domenici, D., Laurencich Minelli, L., 2014. Domingo de Betanzos’ Gifts to Pope Clement VII in 1532-1533: Tracking the Early History of Some Mexican Objects and Codices in Italy., in: *Los Obsequios de Domingo de Betanzos al Papa Clemente VII En 1532-1533: Siguiendo La Historia de Algunos Objetos y Códices Mexicanos En Italia*, Estudios de Cultura Náhuatl. pp. 169–209.
- Driscoll, M.J., Pierazzo, E. (Eds.), 2016. Digital Scholarly Editing: Theories and Practices, 1st ed, Digital Humanities Series. Open Book Publishers, Cambridge, UK. <https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0095>
- Fanini, B., Ferdani, D., Demetrescu, E., Berto, S., d’Annibale, E., 2021. ATON: An Open-Source Framework for Creating Immersive, Collaborative and Liquid Web-Apps for Cultural Heritage. *Applied Sciences* 11, 11062. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112211062>
- Hurdeman, H., Piccoli, C., 2021. 3D Reconstructions as Research Hubs: Geospatial Interfaces for Real-Time Data Exploration of Seventeenth-Century Amsterdam Domestic Interiors. *Open Archaeology* 7, 314–336. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opar-2020-0142>

- Katifori, A., Karvounis, M., Kourtis, V., Perry, S., Roussou, M., Ioanidis, Y., 2018. Applying Interactive Storytelling in Cultural Heritage: Opportunities, Challenges and Lessons Learned, in: Rouse, R., Koenitz, H., Haahr, M. (Eds.), *Interactive Storytelling, Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 603–612. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04028-4_70
- Knazook, B., Murphy, J., Barner, K., Cassidy, K., Claeysens, S., Cortese, C., Manchester, E.J., Padilla, T., Reijkerker, D., Robson, G., Schmidt, A., Sherratt, T., Warren, M., 2023. WorldFAIR Project (D13.2) Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7897243>
- Laurencich Minelli, L., 1992. *Codice Cospi. Calendario e rituali precolombiani*. Jaca Book, Milano.
- Li, T., 2021. *Interactivity in museums: options for the Aga Khan Museum*. Toronto Metropolitan University. <https://doi.org/10.32920/ryerson.14653479>
- Miliani, C., Domenici, D., Clementi, C., Presciutti, F., Rosi, F., Buti, D., Romani, A., Laurencich Minelli, L., Sgamellotti, A., 2012. Colouring materials of pre-Columbian codices: non-invasive in situ spectroscopic analysis of the Codex Cospi. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 39, 672–679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2011.10.031>
- Moore, J., Rountrey, A., Scates Kettler, H., 2022. *3D Data Creation to Curation: Community Standards for 3D Data Preservation*. ALA.
- Pallud, J., 2017. Impact of interactive technologies on stimulating learning experiences in a museum. *Information & Management* 54, 465–478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2016.10.004>
- Papadopoulos, C., 2024. A Leap of Faith: Revisiting Paradata in 3D Scholarship, in: Huvila, I., Andersson, L., Sköld, O. (Eds.), *Perspectives on Paradata, Knowledge Management and Organizational Learning*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 61–86. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53946-6_4
- Pietroni, E., Chirivì, A., Fanini, B., Bucciero, A., 2023. An Innovative Approach to Shape Information Architecture Related to Ancient Manuscripts, Through Multi-layered Virtual Ecosystems. From Codex4D to DataSpace Project, in: De Paolis, L.T., Arpaia, P., Sacco, M. (Eds.), *Extended Reality, Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, pp. 247–267. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43404-4_16
- Pujol-Tost, L., 2019. Did We Just Travel to the Past? Building and Evaluating With Cultural Presence Different Modes of VR-Mediated Experiences in Virtual Archaeology. *J. Comput. Cult. Herit.* 12, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3230678>
- Rizvic, S., Boskovic, D., Mijatovic, B., 2024. Advanced interactive digital storytelling in digital heritage applications. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 33, e00334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.daach.2024.e00334>
- Robinete, F., Arnaud, R., Parisi, T., Cozzi, P., 2018. glTF: Designing an Open-Standard Runtime Asset Format Fabrice Robinet, Re mi Arnaud, Tony Parisi, and Patrick Cozzi, in: *GPU Pro 360 Guide to 3D Engine Design*. A K Peters/CRC Press, pp. 243–260.
- Schettino, P., Pietroni, E., d’Annibale, E., 2023. Re-Thinking Visitor Experience with Ancient Manuscripts via the Holographic Showcase: The Case of the Codex4D Project and Its First Public Results from a Mixed-Method Evaluation In Situ. *Heritage* 6, 6035–6065. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6090318>
- Schreibman, S., Papadopoulos, C., 2019. Textuality in 3D: three-dimensional (re)constructions as digital scholarly editions. *Int J Digit Humanities* 1, 221–233. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42803-019-00024-6>
- Schreibman, S., Schoueri, K.G., 2024. 3D Digital Scholarly Editions: The Text as Object, in: *Digital Humanities & Heritage*. Presented at the DARIAH-HR International Conference, Kuzman Šlogar, K. & Žugić Borić, A. (eds.), Zadar – Rijeka, Croatia, pp. 15–31.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alice Bordignon: Methodology, Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

Davide Domenici: Investigation, Writing – review & editing